

Forming an expert group for user centred environmental data services

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

Throughout the project, an expert group of 14 individuals across the Environmental Data Service (EDS) and partners was formed. The group met regularly to share good practice, generate ideas, track progress and solve problems. At the end of the project, the team undertook a retrospective exercise where we identified the benefits, challenges and surprises of working together. Overall this group was a success and we plan to evolve into a core EDS working group to continue this work.

Rationale for the work

The EDS is a UK-based initiative funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) to manage, preserve, and provide access to environmental data collected through NERC-funded research and projects. It acts as an overarching umbrella term for five data centers that specialise in different areas of environmental science, such as atmospheric science, marine science, earth observation, biodiversity, and geoscience. Teams are distributed across many UK locations.

The EDS plays a critical role in ensuring that valuable environmental data is accessible to researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders for use in scientific analysis, policy development, and decision-making. It also promotes data sharing and reuse, which supports open science and helps advance research in areas like climate change, ecosystem health, and natural hazards. Key goals of the EDS include long-term data preservation, compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, and the facilitation of interdisciplinary research by making data from different domains accessible through a unified framework.

One of the core aims of the EDS is to better engage with users and ensure their needs are central to everything we do. How we design, develop, maintain and share our data services hasn't traditionally been prioritised with user feedback in mind. Many of our teams and systems are now having to change the way we work and learn new skills.

The [Nielsen Norman Group](#), a globally trusted team of user experience experts, state there are [six levels of maturity stages](#) for embedding user centred approaches within organisations (Figure 1).

The EDS’s maturity stage is varied across individual teams. To advance maturity of user centred approaches towards level six, the EDS need consistent research and design methods, a culture of knowledge sharing, measurable outcomes and strong leadership.

The BOOST EDS project wanted to tackle this head on, by identifying existing knowledge and challenges, gathering and sharing good practice, and building a network of experts. At the beginning of the BOOST project, the EDS was at stage two.

Following the project, we are now firmly in stage three.

Figure 1: the six levels of user experience maturity, as defined by the Nielsen Norman Group: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ux-maturity-model/>

Methodology

Interested individuals across the EDS were identified during a workshop with 24 experts to discuss barriers to designing and implementing user centred data services ([see detailed workshop findings](#)). The workshop was used as a collaborative way to identify, shape and prioritise the work for the remainder of the project.

Table 1 includes a list of core individuals involved and their role in the group. The group met online monthly from May 2025 and discussed the priorities and direction of the project work.

Table 1: a summary of the core EDS expert group

First name	Role in group	Email
Poppy Townsend	Work package lead, meeting chair, representative for Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, National Centre for Atmospheric Science, National Centre for Earth Observation	poppy.townsend@stfc.ac.uk
Carl Watson	Representative for National Geoscience Data Centre, British Geological Survey	cats@bgs.ac.uk
Paulius Tvaranavicius	Representative for National Geoscience Data Centre, British Geological Survey	pautva@bgs.ac.uk
Monica Hanley	Representative for British Oceanographic Data Centre, National Oceanography Centre	monhan@noc.ac.uk
Matt McCormack	Representative for British Oceanographic Data Centre, National Oceanography Centre	matcor@noc.ac.uk
Jesse Alexander	Representative for Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, National Centre for Atmospheric Science, National Centre for Earth Observation	jesse.alexander@stfc.ac.uk
Thomas Zwagerman	Representative for UK Polar Data Centre, British Antarctic Survey	thozwa@bas.ac.uk
Louise Darroch	Representative for British Oceanographic Data Centre, National Oceanography Centre	lorr@noc.ac.uk
David Green	Representative for Environmental Information Data Centre, UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology	dgreen@ceh.ac.uk
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Lessons learnt

The group met regularly to share good practice, generate ideas, track progress and solve problems. Table 2 summarises the lessons learnt from the project, categorised into benefits, challenges and surprises.

Table 2: A summary of the benefits, challenges and surprises from the work were identified by members of the expert group during a retrospective discussion at the end of the project

Finding type	Project finding	Theme/s
Benefit	Being part of a network of peers with similar interest and expertise levels who can offer support and guidance.	People and communities
Benefit	Practical resources created were well received and are being used in day-to-day work.	Information management
Benefit	Knowledge exchange amongst peers improved via the creation of the expert user group.	Information management
Benefit	Structured group meetings with good facilitation led to useful discussions and actionable tasks.	Information management
Benefit	Central mechanism for information sharing e.g. within meetings or via the shared project document system.	Information management
Benefit	Gathering broad views from across multiple disciplines provided potential opportunities for future projects.	Processes, governance and strategy
Benefit	Gathering broad views from across multiple disciplines helped us to frame ideas and narrative for this report.	People and communities / Processes, governance and strategy
Challenge	Working on individual case studies, per data centre, reinforced siloed working.	People and communities / Processes, governance and strategy
Challenge	Time constraints due to short project length - varying levels of user centred approaches were implemented.	People and communities
Challenge	Lack of wider project management and collaboration across work packages.	Processes, governance and strategy

Challenge	Unclear scope and high level objectives for the work package meant these had to be defined by the expert group as the project progressed. This limited the amount of time to actually undertake the work.	Processes, governance and strategy
Challenge	Sheer amount of information to collate and synthesise in a short time period.	Information management
Challenge	No/limited control of resource allocations of staff in other data centres. Some members of the expert group were not explicitly funded by the BOOST project. Made delegating work package tasks difficult.	Processes, governance and strategy
Surprise	The number of people with a shared interest in co-creation/user centred approaches.	People and communities
Surprise	All individuals/teams (both internal and external to the EDS) face similar challenges to implementing user centred approaches.	People and communities
Surprise	Complex jargon which has different meanings for different audiences (UX Designer, Research Software Engineer, Data Scientist).	Information management
Surprise	The benefits of talking across multiple domains e.g. advice and guidance, creation and framing of new ideas, sharing knowledge and resources, collaboration opportunities.	People and communities
Surprise	Different opinions about 'formalising' user centred approaches, especially for internal only projects.	People and communities

Opportunities and future recommendations

- Set up a consultant group of experts within the EDS for user centred approaches
- Organise in person networking for people interested in user centred approaches to environmental data projects.
- Explore creative ways to outsource user research work
- Pilot using holacracy software to define and visualise the diverse roles and expertise of staff across the EDS - using this expert group as a test case
- Turn the beta toolkit into a fully supported operational EDS service with appropriate governance and dedicated resource for building upon the work so far
- Disseminate the findings from this work to priority stakeholders (using the EDS stakeholder map to identify priorities)
- Create an ongoing base of user research undertaken in environmental data domains